

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

SLIT2

(slit guidance ligand 2)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	9353 / O94813
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD, AMP-AD
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Therapeutic Area(s)	Alzheimer's disease
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CONTENTS OF TEP

Bioinformatic analysis: Target source & hypothesis

Protein constructs & expression methods: EGF-like domain of Human SLIT2 produced in Expi293F cells

TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a TMT proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 42) contains several novel AD targets, including SMOC1 and SFRP1 (1,2).

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 3.93 (rank #494, 98th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate

these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

Overall	rank	pctl	GeneticsScore	OmicsScore
3.929	495	98.01	1.966	1.963

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 3.93 out of 5 (rank #495, 98th percentile). The individual score components include 1.97 of 3 for genetics, and 1.96 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of SLIT2 protein is significantly increased and RNA is significantly decreased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target

categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. SLIT2 is annotated to GO terms from the Synapse, Vasculature, Structural Stabilization, Immune Response, and Apoptosis domains.

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer's Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low confidence measures of expression. The expression of SLIT2 is confidently detected in oligodendrocytes, vascular and leptomenigeal cells (VLAMC), and both excitatory and inhibitory neuron sub-types within this dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

SLIT2 is an axon guidance protein that promotes accurate wiring of the brain during development and post-injury (3,4) and over-expression in mouse induces some AD like pathology (5). While it is unknown whether SLIT2 is directly involved in AD, it was identified in proteomic studies of AD brain as part of a core AD pathology associated co-expression module. The goal of this project is to provide resources to the scientific community to advance the future investigations into SLIT2 through the provision of purified

protein, validated antibodies, and a bioinformatic workup of SLIT2 as part of the target enablement package (TEP) available to interested investigators in academia or the pharmaceutical industry.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Slit guidance ligand 2 (SLIT2) is a sizable axon guidance and repulsion protein consisting of 1529 amino acids, which is secreted into the extracellular space (6–8). The protein comprises 20 leucine-rich repeat regions (LRR) and 7 EGF-like domains (Uniprot: O94813), conferring signalling properties through its interaction with the Robo family of single-pass transmembrane receptors (7). SLIT2 plays a pivotal role in axonal guidance during development, ensuring the midline partitioning of retinal axons, guiding connections from the midbrain to the cortex (7,9,10). The interplay between SLIT family members and Robo receptors may yield diverse effects in different biological systems, with evidence suggesting that both SLIT1 and SLIT2 may regulate angiogenesis and tumor growth (11–14), and SLIT2 may also regulate immune chemotaxis and have a modulatory role upon neuroinflammation (15–18). The transcriptional inactivation of SLIT2, similar to SLIT1, through promoter hypermethylation is prevalent in tumor cells, likely as a mechanism to inhibit its tumor-suppressive functions during metastasis (13,14,19,20).

While the connection between SLIT2 and Alzheimer's disease (AD) remains unclear, SLIT2, modulates both neuroimmune migration (15,21) and plays a role in both synapse formation and activity gating (10,22,23). The modulatory role of SLIT2 in vascular development and angiogenesis is also observed in SLIT2 transgenic mice, in which blood brain permeability is increased, producing some AD-like brain pathology (5,24,25). Moreover, SLIT2 was identified in a comprehensive proteomic analysis of AD brains versus healthy controls, appearing in a small co-expression module linked to cognitive decline and pathological progression in AD (2). The role of the SLIT family in synapse formation during development may persist into adulthood, contributing to synaptic maintenance, plasticity, and the facilitation of new or strengthened neuronal connections (3,4). This could impact synaptic durability and resilience during the onset and progression of pathogenesis in AD. Although the relationship between SLIT2 and AD remains speculative, the resources developed here aim to assist the scientific community in exploring and unravelling the potential involvement of SLIT2 in AD.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Proteins Purified

1. SLIT2A-c003: EGF-like domain of Human SLIT2 (E921-E1529). Contains a C-terminal 6His and AviTag (allowing in vitro biotinylation, if needed). Protein produced in Expi293F cells.

See **Additional information (section 1)** with details of plasmid expression constructs and purification procedures.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further investigation of the role of SLIT2a in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

Additional Information

Materials and Methods

Protein expression constructs and protein purification

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

1. SLIT2A-c003: EGF-like domain of Human SLIT2 (E921-E1529). Contains a C-terminal 6His and AviTag (allowing in vitro biotinylation, if needed). Protein produced in Expi293F cells.

Construct ID	SLIT2A-c003
Parental vector	pHL-avitag3
Tag	C-terminal His6, C-terminal Avitag
Protein mass (with tag and secretion signal)	73265.4 Da
Extinction Coefficient (M⁻¹ cm⁻¹)	49280
Protein sequence (with tag)	MGILPSGMPALLSLVSLLSVLLMGCVAETGPCLSNPCKNDGTCNSDPVDFYRCTCPYGFKG QDCDVPIHACISNPCKHGGTCHLKEGEEDGFWCICADGFEGENCEVNVDDCEDNDCENN STCVDGINNYTCLPPEYTGELCEEKLDCAQDLNCPQHDSKILTPKGFKCDCTPGYVGEHC DIDFDDCQDNKCKNGAHCTDAVNGYTCICPEGYSGLFCEFSPPMVLPRTSPCDNFDCQNG AQCIVRINEPICQLPGYQGEKCEKLVSVNFINKESYLQIPSAKVRPQTNITLQIATDEDSGILLY KGDKDHIARELYRGRVRSYDYGSHPASAIYSVETINDGNFHVIVELLALDQSLSLSDGGNPKI ITNLSKQSTLNFDSPLYVGGMPGKSNVASLRQAPGQNGTSFHGCIRNLYINSELQDFQKVP MQTGILPGCEPCHKKVCAHGTCQPSSQAGFTCECEQEGWMGPLCDQRTNDPCLGNKCVH GTCLPINAFSYSCKLEGHGGVLCDEEEDLFNPCQAIKCKHKGKRLSGLGQPYCECSSGYTGD SCDREISCRGERIRDYYQKQGYAACQTTKKVSRLECRGGCAGGQCCGPLRSKRRKYSFECT DGSSFVDEVEKVVKCGCTRCVSGTGGSGGSLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGRTKHHHHHH

Purified Protein

<p>Size Exclusion Chromatography: SLIT2A-c003 (with tag)</p>	
<p>Intact Mass Deconvolution: SLIT2A-c003 (with tag)</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Observed Mass:</p>	
<p>Protein yield:</p>	<p>5 mg/L of culture</p>

<p>Expression and Purification Protocol</p>	
<p>Expression host</p>	<p><i>Mammalian:</i> Expi293F cells (Thermo Fisher Scientific)</p>
<p>Expression medium</p>	<p>FreeStyle 293 Expression Medium (Thermo Fisher Scientific)</p>
<p>Plasmid purification</p>	<p>Transform the construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain MACH1. Plate on LB-agar plates containing ampicillin (100 µg/ml). Inoculate 5 ml LB broth containing ampicillin (100 µg/ml) with a single colony and grow 6h at 37°C with shaking. Inoculate 800 ml LB broth containing the same antibiotic with 2 ml of starter culture and grow overnight at 37°C with shaking. Split culture into 4 and perform MaxiPrep (Qiagen) with 4 columns according to manufacturer’s instructions. Add 0.7 volumes of isopropanol to precipitate the plasmid. Spin (17000g, 30 min, 4°C) and wash pellet with 70% ethanol.</p>

	Resuspend plasmid with sterile TE buffer under sterile conditions. Yield is typically 2 mg of plasmid.
Transfection	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Split Expi293F cells to 1×10^6 cells/ml in 200 ml FreeStyle 293 Expression Medium. Incubate for 24 h until cells are approximately 2×10^6 cells/ml (37°C, 150 rpm, 8% CO₂, 75% rh). 2. Add plasmid to 4mL of pre-warmed Opti-MEM at 0.5 µg/ml final concentration. 3. Add linear PEI (1 mg/ml sterile stock) to another 4mL of pre-warmed Opti-MEM at 3 µg/ml final concentration. 4. Add the mixture from Step 3 to the one in Step 2 and incubate at room temperature for 30 min. 5. Add the plasmid/PEI mixture slowly to the cells. 6. Add sodium butyrate (1 M sterile stock) to 12 mM final concentration. 7. Incubate cells at 30°C (8%CO₂/75% rh) with shaking at 150 rpm. 8. Harvest cell culture supernatant at 5 days post transfection (900g, 20 min, 4°C). 9. Filter supernatant through 0.2 µm filter.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ni IMAC W10 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol 2. Ni IMAC W25 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 25 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol 3. Ni IMAC elution buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 250 mM imidazole, 2% glycerol 4. Size exclusion chromatography elution buffer : dPBS (from ThermoFisher) 5. Ni-sepharose beads, equilibrated in Ni IMAC W10 buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Add imidazole to filtered supernatant to 10 mM final concentration. 2. Add a total of 2.5 ml equilibrated Ni-sepharose beads to the cell supernatant, split into 50-ml falcon tubes. Mix by rotation for 1 hr in a cold room. 3. Spin beads/supernatant slurry (700g, 5 min, 4°C). Decant supernatant and wash beads with 100 ml W10 buffer. Repeat wash with 50 ml W10. Spin again and transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 4. Wash column with 25 ml W25. 5. Elute protein with 1x 10 ml elution buffer, followed by 2x5 ml elution buffer. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay. Pool elution fractions containing protein.
Purification step 2: Size Exclusion Chromatography	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Concentrate pooled IMAC elution fractions to 1 ml using a centrifugal concentrator with the appropriate MWCO. 2. Perform SEC on a HiLoad Superdex S200 HR 16/60 column, equilibrated in DPBS, at 1 ml/min. 3. Analyse fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 1-5 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy. 4. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C.

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